

THE INFLUENCE OF TEACHER FEEDBACK ON STUDENT ACHIEVEMENT

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Abstract. This study aims to investigate how teacher feedback influences students' academic performance. Article includes clear explanation of types of feedbacks which are more effective ones for today's methodology highlighting other researches that tested pupils' and teachers' attitude on feedback. The methodology has focused on gathering information through secondary descriptive method. Study observed data of researches done during previous years on the effect of teachers' feedback on students' academic achievement. The findings from the analysis were utilized to create a feedback system that could improve its impact on teaching and learning in classrooms. Research has consistently demonstrated that all types of feedback have a positive impact on students, as evidenced by the analysis of numerous studies.

Keywords: Feedback, methodology, communication

Аннотация. Целью данного исследования является изучение того, как обратная связь учителей влияет на академическую успеваемость учащихся. Статья включает четкое объяснение типов обратной связи, которые являются более эффективными для современной методологии, а также другие исследования, в которых проверялось отношение учеников и учителей к обратной связи. Методология ориентирована на сбор информации с помощью вторичного описательного метода. Изучены данные исследований, проведенных в предыдущие годы, о влиянии обратной связи учителей на успеваемость учащихся. Результаты анализа были использованы для создания системы обратной связи, которая могла бы улучшить ее влияние на преподавание и обучение в классах. Исследования последовательно продемонстрировали, что все виды обратной связи оказывают положительное влияние на студентов, о чем свидетельствует анализ многочисленных исследований.

Ключевые слова: Обратная связь, методология, коммуникация.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot o'qituvchining fikr-mulohazalari talabalarning akademik faoliyatiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Maqolada o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilarning fikr-mulohazalarga munosabatini sinab ko'rgan boshqa tadqiqotlarni yoritib, bugungi metodologiya uchun samaraliroq bo'lgan teskari aloqa turlarining aniq izohi mavjud. Metodologiya ikkinchi darajali tavsiflash usuli orqali ma'lumot to'plashga qaratilgan. O'qituvchilarning fikr-mulohazalari talabalarning o'quv yutuqlariga ta'siri bo'yicha o'tgan yillar davomida olib borilgan tadqiqotlarning kuzatilgan ma'lumotlarini o'rganish. Tahlil natijalaridan uning sinflarda o'qitish va o'rganishga ta'sirini yaxshilashi mumkin bo'lgan qayta aloqa tizimini yaratish uchun foydalanildi. Tadqiqotlar doimiy ravishda fikr-mulohazalarning barcha turlari o'quvchilarga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishini ko'rsatdi, buni ko'plab tadqiqotlar tahlili tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Teskari aloqa, metodologiya, aloqa

Introduction

Feedback is details on how an individual or group is doing compared to a particular goal or set of expectations. It can be given through spoken remarks, written assessments, or non-verbal signals. Feedback is commonly utilized to assist individuals or teams in enhancing their performance, making changes, and attaining superior outcomes. Teacher feedback during classes

involves teachers providing information, comments, and guidance to students about their performance and understanding of the material. This feedback can be given verbally, through written comments, or during activities to help students improve and stay motivated. Effective feedback is specific, constructive, and actionable, focusing on guiding students to enhance their skills and knowledge. It helps students understand their strengths and areas for improvement in various aspects of learning. Overall, timely and personalized feedback from teachers supports students in achieving their learning goals and developing a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

In order to analyze effect of feedback types of it should be browsed:

1. **Positive Feedback:** This involves acknowledging and praising students for their efforts, achievements, and strengths to boost their confidence and motivation.
2. **Constructive Feedback:** Teachers offer specific suggestions for improvement, point out areas where students can enhance their performance, and provide guidance on how to do so.
3. **Corrective Feedback:** This type of feedback helps students identify and address errors or misconceptions in their understanding of the material to deepen their knowledge.
4. **Descriptive Feedback:** Teachers give detailed information about students' performance, highlighting what they did well and areas where they can improve without necessarily providing a specific solution.
5. **Formative Feedback:** Ongoing feedback provided throughout the learning process helps students monitor their progress, set goals, and make adjustments to improve their performance.
6. **Summative Feedback:** Given at the end of an assessment or learning activity, this feedback provides an overall evaluation of students' performance and outcomes.
7. **Peer Feedback:** Encouraging students to provide feedback to each other promotes collaboration, communication skills, and a deeper understanding of the material.
8. **Self-Reflection Feedback:** Students are encouraged to reflect on their own performance, identify strengths and weaknesses, set improvement goals, and develop self-regulation skills.

These different types of feedback serve specific purposes and can be utilized strategically by teachers to support student learning and growth effectively.

Literature review

Teacher feedback is an important aspect of the educational process since it has a substantial impact on student achievement (A. M. M Mahmudul Hasan, 2024). Students who receive regular as well as timely feedback from teachers tend to do better in their studies (Madigan & Kim, 2021). Many studies, including these, feedback has positive effect on students' academic achievement. According to Guardia et al (2019), receiving prompt feedback from teachers assists students in comprehending their expectations. They persist in making efforts to improve their academic performance, as well as their social behavior and relationships with others. Every student progresses at their own pace in academics, and providing positive or optimistic feedback can help boost their confidence levels. It can be seen in studies by Ye & Liu, 2023, that clear and achievable expectations set by teachers can help students receive more effective feedback following exams or projects.

The teacher's awareness is crucial in this process, as they should be knowledgeable about the appropriate methods of giving feedback tailored to the individual characteristics of their students. As Dahal et al (2022) mentioned that, Providing helpful feedback can help students see how they are doing, find areas to improve, and inspire them to continue learning. Different techniques and types of feedback are mentioned in Introduction section.

Method

The research methodology involved gathering information through a secondary descriptive approach. Various studies and researches were examined to collect data for analysis. The collected data was presented in a descriptive manner, and the authors described different results.

Results and discussion

The findings indicated that feedback has several positive impacts on students' academic performance, including their social life during studies and overall academic success. The studies discussed in the analysis acknowledged that feedback is a crucial factor during the student years. It not only serves as a motivator for students but also encourages them to address mistakes and weaknesses with pride.

Feedback is an essential construct for many theories of learning and instruction, and an understanding of the conditions for effective feedback should facilitate both theoretical development and instructional practice (Bangert-Drowns, R.L., Kulik, C.L., Kulik, J.A., & Morgan, M.T., 1991 "The instructional effect of feedback in test-like events"). Studies consistently demonstrate that constructive, specific, and timely feedback from teachers can boost students' motivation, self-confidence, and academic achievements. Well-crafted feedback helps students recognize their strengths and areas for improvement, leading to increased interest in learning and higher levels of success.

Nevertheless, the effectiveness of teacher feedback depends on its quality. A model of feedback is then proposed that identifies the particular properties and circumstances that make it effective, and some typically thorny issues are discussed, including the timing of feedback and the effects of positive and negative feedback (J Hattie, H Timperley, 2007 "The power of feedback"). Feedback that is unclear, overly critical, or inconsistent may not produce the desired outcomes. The mechanisms responsible for such facilitation are frequently misunderstood, and one can find numerous examples in both research and instructional development where feedback is used inappropriately, neutralizing any positive effects it might have on student performance (Kulhavy, R.W. and Stock, W.A. , 1989 "Feedback in written instruction: The place of response certitude"). Therefore, it is vital for teachers to receive training on delivering feedback that is tailored to each student's unique needs and learning objectives.

Teacher feedback significantly influences students' attitudes toward learning and their academic accomplishments. Through providing high-quality feedback, educators can empower students to take charge of their learning journey and make substantial progress toward their educational aspirations.

Conclusion

The exchange of feedback between teachers and students plays a crucial role in enhancing academic performance. When teachers provide constructive feedback to students, it not only helps them improve their understanding of the subject but also boosts their confidence and motivation to excel. This continuous feedback loop creates a supportive learning environment that encourages students to persevere through challenges and strive for excellence. By investing in teacher training and promoting a culture of constructive feedback in schools, we can significantly impact student achievement and overall academic success. Recognizing the importance of teacher feedback can lead to positive outcomes for both students and educators, setting the stage for a brighter future in education.

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